

A Search for Pulsations in M Dwarfs in 20-second Cadence TESS Data

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ABSTRACT

Asteroseismology is a powerful tool in probing the internal structure and ages of solar-type and red-giant stars, through the study of oscillations detectable in photometric and spectroscopic observations. As of yet though, it has not been successfully applied to low mass stars. We present the results of a search for solar-like oscillations in M dwarf stars observed by TESS in the 20-second cadence mode. Our analysis covers all M dwarfs between $0.1M_{\odot}$ and $0.3M_{\odot}$ within 15pc listed in the catalog of [Winters et al. \(2021\)](#), comprising 512 in total, as well as an extended sample of 705 stars based on the Fifth Catalogue of Nearby Stars and the All-sky Catalogue of Bright M Dwarfs ([Golovin et al. 2023](#), [Lépine & Gaidos 2011](#)). Of these 1217 stars, 868 of them had at least one corresponding 20-second TESS observation. We probe frequencies up to the Nyquist frequency of $25000 \mu\text{Hz}$, making this study the largest sample size and highest time-resolution search for pulsations in M dwarfs to date. We quantify the sensitivity of our search through signal injection and recovery tests of synthetic oscillations. Our detection thresholds are between 10 – 40 parts per million (ppm) for 54% of stars in our combined sample and between 1-10 ppm for 38% of them. We reach detection thresholds between 0.2-1 ppm for nine of the stars in our sample. We co-add the power spectra of M dwarfs with similar masses to search for signals that might be too noisy to detect in individual stars and discuss the efficacy of this method. The analysis reveals no clear solar-like oscillations for any of the M dwarfs in our sample, suggesting that the driving mechanisms behind oscillations in M dwarfs do not produce large enough amplitudes to be observable with the current photometric precision of TESS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Asteroseismology is the study of stars through small oscillations visible on their surface. These oscillations are stochastically driven and damped by the turbulent motion of gas in the outer convective layers. Over the past several years, asteroseismology has proven to be a highly effective method of probing stellar interiors and deriving physical properties of stars. The spectra of these oscillations is characterized by a typical Gaussian-like envelope, and they can be primarily described by their large frequency separation ($\Delta\nu$) and frequency at maximum power (ν_{max}). $\Delta\nu$, the distance between primary peaks in the power spectrum, corresponds to the time for acoustic waves to travel back and forth through the stellar interior (and thus depends on the density). It is also possible to measure a second set of peaks in the spectra characterized by their small separation $\delta\nu_l$ ([Roxburgh & Vorontsov 2003](#)). The small frequency separation is sensitive to the sound-speed gradient and thus the chemical composition gradient in the core regions of the star, providing information on its evolutionary state ([Di Mauro 2016](#)). When these parameters are combined with a measure of a star's effective surface temperature,

T_{eff} , the ages, masses, and radii of solar stars can be determined within 10%, 5%, and 3% respectively ([Moya 2013](#)).

One can predict the frequency and structure of solar-like oscillations by linearly perturbing the equations defining a star's mechanical equilibrium. Both high frequency p modes and low frequency g modes can be found in the spectra of solar oscillations. The p modes are acoustic, seismic waves, while the g modes are gravitational ones that occur in any stratified medium ([Di Mauro 2016](#)). They are named after the forces that act to restore the perturbed stellar equilibrium. The spatial configuration of these modes is described using spherical harmonics, i.e. the radial overtone, n ; the degree, ℓ ; and the azimuthal order, m . The two methods to detect these oscillations are photometry and spectroscopy; the former measuring the brightness perturbations of a star caused by stellar oscillations, the latter measuring the outward and inward movement of the stellar surface ([Di Mauro 2016](#)). The primary nonradial modes observable from light variations are the $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$ modes, although up to $\ell = 4$ can be detected in radial velocity measurements. It is difficult to detect g modes in

cooler stochastic pulsators as they cannot propagate in the thick outer convection zones (Kurtz 2022).

Solar-like oscillations are predicted to occur in all main-sequence and post main sequence stars cool enough to have a convective envelope (i.e. stars with $T_{\text{eff}} < 6700$ K). Indeed, observations have confirmed them to be present in main sequence stars (Chaplin et al. 2014), subgiants (Mathur et al. 2022), and red giants (Bedding et al. 2010). As of yet though, no detection of solar-like oscillations in M dwarfs have been found, and the lowest mass stars with detected oscillations seem to be around $0.8M_{\odot}$ (Serenelli et al. 2017). Being the coolest stars on the main sequence, M dwarfs are completely convective for $M < 0.3M_{\odot}$ (Rodríguez-López et al. 2014), and have large convective envelopes (up to half the radius of the star), at higher masses. As such, they have the potential to exhibit solar-like oscillations, and are predicted to do so.

Making up more than 70% of the stars in our galaxy, M-dwarfs are the largest class of stars. However, some of their fundamental parameters remain uncertain, with measured values disagreeing with models (Hillenbrand & White 2004, Chabrier et al. 2007). An observational discovery of solar-like oscillations would open the door for applying asteroseismology methods to them, and allow us to study their interiors in more detail. In addition, M dwarfs are often favored when searching for planets (Nutzman & Charbonneau 2008, Dressing & Charbonneau 2015), and to date many exoplanets are known to orbit them (Hensley 2019). Understanding these stars and their fundamental parameters in more detail would also provide a better picture of the planetary systems they host.

2. M DWARF PULSATION MECHANISMS

Several types of pulsations, with various excitation mechanisms and periods, are predicted for M dwarfs. Multiple theoretical studies have predicted that the fundamental radial mode of low mass stars can be excited through the nuclear burning of ^3He or deuterium, through a process known as the ϵ -mechanism. Rodríguez-López et al. (2014) solved the complete non-adiabatic pulsations equations, and found that the fundamental radial mode is unstable over the whole mass range, with the ϵ -mechanism producing fundamental and low-degree ($l < 3$) p -modes with with periods between 20 min and 1 h for stars in the 0.20 - 0.60 M_{\odot} mass range.

The second primary type of pulsation expected in M dwarfs are the stochastically driven solar-like oscillations, which are present in other main sequence stars. We can estimate the periods and spacings of these os-

M M_{\odot}	ν_{max} μHz	$\Delta\nu_{\text{max}}$ μHz	$P_{\nu_{\text{max}}}$ min
0.5 - 0.6	8000-6000	275-215	2-3
0.35 - 0.5	9500-8000	330-275	1-2
0.2 - 0.35	12000-9500	455-330	1-2
0.1 - 0.2	20000-12000	735-455	1-2

Table 1. Expected ν_{max} and $\Delta\nu$ parameters from solar-like oscillation scaling relations. Note that these scaling relations have not been calibrated for M dwarfs, and will only be calibrated once solar-like oscillations are detected.

cillations using the scaling relations first presented by Kjeldsen & Bedding (1995):

$$\Delta\nu_0 = (M/M_{\odot})^{1/2} (R/R_{\odot})^{-3/2} 134.9\mu\text{Hz} \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_{\text{max}} = \frac{M/M_{\odot}}{(R/R_{\odot})^2 \sqrt{T_{\text{eff}}/5777\text{K}}} 3.05\text{mHz}, \quad (2)$$

where we take $T_{\text{eff}} = 5777$ K. Taking representative masses, radii, and effective surface temperatures of M dwarfs from Pecaute & Mamajek (2013), we estimate the expected $\Delta\nu$ and ν_{max} for different mass stars in our sample (Table 1). While the empirical scaling relations we use here have not been calibrated for M dwarfs, which can be completely convective as opposed to only partially so, the expected periods based off these relations agree well with those determined by Rodríguez-López et al. (2014) using a different method. We see that to fully search for solar-like oscillations in M dwarfs, frequencies up to approximately 20000 μHz must be explored. This is only now possible with the high cadence data from the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (*TESS*), which allows us to search for oscillations up to 25000 μHz .

We use similar scaling relations to predict the amplitudes of oscillations in M dwarfs. We follow the methods of Chaplin et al. (2011), which are themselves based on the above relations. The estimated maximum rms amplitude of the radial modes can be scaled from the solar value by

$$A_{\text{max}}^{\text{rms}} = A_{\text{max},\odot}^{\text{rms}} \beta \left(\frac{L}{L_{\odot}} \right) \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff},\odot}} \right)^{-2}, \quad (3)$$

where $A_{\text{max},\odot} = 2.1$ ppm in the *TESS* bandpass. The factor of β is a correction factor for the decrease in amplitudes of the hottest stars. For our purposes we set it

equal to unity. As before, this scaling relation has not been calibrated for M dwarfs which have much larger convective envelopes. The expected amplitudes based off these relations are very small though, between 0.2 - 1 ppm. These low amplitudes are what have made the detection of these oscillations so challenging.

The last properties of these oscillations important to note are the lifetimes of the modes that compose them, as we want to ensure that they do not dissipate and get re-excited over the course of a *TESS* observation. As shown in Chaplin et al. (2009), the lifetime of a mode is inversely proportional to the temperature of the star to the fourth power. For M dwarfs the lifetimes are expected in the several 10s of days. This is important for the low temperature M dwarfs in our study, as it confirms that their mode lifetimes are sufficiently long for us to stitch together consecutive sectors and establish a longer baseline (as has successfully been done in other studies for higher temperature stars, such as Chontos et al. 2021).

3. OBSERVATIONAL SEARCH

Much of the advances in stellar pulsation work in recent years has been due to the success of space missions with high-quality photometry, such as *Kepler* which produced data with cadences as short as 1 min. Previous studies have searched for both of the kinds of M dwarf pulsations described above in the *Kepler* database (Rodríguez-López et al. 2015, Rodríguez et al. 2016), but with no success. Their search was limited by the Nyquist frequency of the *Kepler* SC mode data, $f_{\text{Nyq}} = 8547 \mu\text{Hz}$.

With periods expected as low as 1-3 min, probing the high frequency space where M-dwarf solar oscillations are predicted was not possible until recently, with the advent of the *TESS* mission and its very short cadence data. *TESS* has provided photometric light curves for over 300,000 stars, producing a dataset of potential solar-like oscillators that has yet to be fully explored. Specifically, its 20-second cadence data has shown strong potential in asteroseismology and the detection of solar-oscillations (Huber et al. 2022).

TESS observes the sky in sectors with an average observation duration of 27.4 d, with periodic gaps of less than 16 hours every 13.7 d when data is downlinked at perigee. *TESS* covers 2304 deg² on the sky per pointing (Fausnaugh et al. 2019), with relatively large pixels (21" × 21"). The majority of targets are observed in one or two sectors, with targets having higher number of observations the closer they fall to the ecliptic poles. Stars located directly on these poles, known as the continuous viewing zones, have observing periods of just over 100

Figure 1. The selected S_2 sample based on the $(J - H, H - K, J - K)$ photometry cuts of the CNS5 catalog. Colored black are all the stars in the catalog, orange are those that passed the photometry cuts, and red are those with masses $> 0.3M_{\odot}$.

days (Ricker et al. 2014). *TESS* observed these stars in 30 minute cadences, and later at 10 minutes. A subset of these sectors with stars flagged as astroseismic candidates were observed at higher cadence 120-second integration times. *TESS*'s extended mission further introduced an even shorter 20-second mode for a reduced target list. This data offers the best chances at detecting solar oscillations in less evolved stars, such as M dwarfs.

4. TARGET SAMPLE

The most promising M dwarf targets for an oscillation search are those closest to us and brightest. Our initial sample of M dwarfs thus consists of the catalogue compiled by Winters et al. (2021), which lists 512 M dwarfs with masses from 0.1-0.3 M_{\odot} within 15 pc. We call this initial sample S_1 . We further expand our sample by considering all M dwarfs up to masses of $0.64M_{\odot}$. We call this sample S_2 . To compile it, we first use the Fifth Catalogue of Nearby Stars (CNS5) to identify all stars with parallaxes larger than 40 mas (Golovin et al. 2023). We use the 2MASS J, H , and K_s bands listed in CNS5 to perform color cuts designed to select M dwarfs. Namely, we require that $J - H < 0.75$, $H - K > 0.1$ and $0.7 < J - K < 1.1$, as well as that $5 < K < 10$. This returned 2988 stars, visible in Figure 1. We further expand our sample S_2 using the all-sky catalog of bright M dwarfs from Lépine & Gaidos (2011), which lists 8,889 M dwarfs with apparent infrared magnitude $J < 10$. These come from the SUPERBLINK survey (Lépine 2016), supplemented by the Tycho-2 catalog. While the majority of the stars in this catalog overlap with the ones we obtain from photometry cuts of CNS5,

Figure 2. Mass distributions of the stars in our S_2 sample. In blue are noted the single stars, in red the primary companions, and in purple the secondary companions. Error bars on each bin are Poisson.

there are 16 bright M dwarfs that fall slightly beyond 25 pc. We include these in our S_2 sample.

For our combined star sample of these two catalogs, we restrict our sample to M dwarfs with masses from $0.3-0.64M_\odot$. We use the relation presented in [Benedict et al. \(2016\)](#) to estimate the masses of the stars in our sample using their absolute 2MASS K_S -band magnitude M_K .

$$\mathcal{M} = C_0 + C_1 (M_K - x_0) + C_2 (M_K - x_0)^2 + C_3 (M_K - x_0)^3 + C_4 (M_K - x_0)^4$$

Here, the parameters $C_0 = 0.2311$, $C_1 = 0.1352$, $C_2 = .04$, $C_3 = .0038$, $C_4 = .0032$, and $x_0 = 7.5$, which were derived from fits to 47 M dwarfs whose masses were precisely measured from a combination of radial velocity and astrometry data. We restrict our focus to M dwarfs with estimated mass greater than $0.3M_\odot$, so as to avoid redundancy with S_1 . This expanded sample consists of 705 unique stars, due to the majority of stars in the two catalogs being of lower mass. The mass distribution of stars in our resulting sample can be seen in [Figure 2](#), along with the distribution of stars in single vs multiple-star systems. This is important as *TESS*'s large pixels can cause blending between nearby stars, which can cause the seismic signal from one star to be combined with that of another.

5. DATA PROCESSING

We download all of the *TESS* 20 s short cadence observations available on our targets from the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescope (MAST). Of our initial sample S_1 of 512 M dwarfs, 481 of them had at least one 20 second cadence (SC) *TESS* observation. Of our larger

Figure 3. Number of 20 second cadence *TESS* observations for stars in our S_1 sample.

sample S_2 , 387 of them had at least one SC observation. For each star, we pass it through the following pre-processing pipeline, which we constructed with the help of functions from the `Lightkurve` Python package ([Barentsen et al. 2021](#)).

- Step 1: Download all of the the POC-processed Pre-data Conditioning Standard Aperture Photometry (PDCSAP) flux light curves available for the star. Create distinct light curve ‘groups’ by stitching together observations in consecutive sectors if more than one observation is present. These stitched light curves have improved detection thresholds, as the noise in the periodogram of a time series decreases as $1/\sqrt{N}$, where N is the number of data points. We do not stich together sectors more than a month apart as the process that excites the solar oscillations is stochastic, such that oscillations phase changes with time and the modes lifetime is finite ([Di Mauro 2016](#)). Modes could be re-excited over long data gaps, impacting the resulting periodogram.
- Step 2: Normalize each of the light curve groups by dividing by the median flux. Perform sigma-clipping using $\sigma = 4$ to remove outliers from the data.
- Step 3: Apply a 2-hour, degree 2 polynomial Savitzky-Golay high-pass filter to remove long-period trends in the data. While other authors use longer high-pass filters when flattening their data ([Chontos et al. 2021](#)), many of the M dwarfs in our sample have clear rotation periods on the order of a few hours, and a shorter high-pass filter is required.
- Step 4: Clean any remaining flare signatures from the flattened data by removing groups of 3 or more con-

Figure 4. Example of analyzed light curve (Gaia DR3 1791995119082190848) and processing applied. Upper Left: Original PDCSAP light curve in units of $e^- s^{-1}$, with visible long-term rotational variability and short-duration flares. Upper Right: Residual light curve after long duration variations and flares are removed, and light curves in multiple consecutive sectors are stitched together. Lower Left: Power spectrum in the $[0, 25000]$ μHz region, with a red line at 4 times the mean noise level. Lower Right: Power spectral density, smoothed with a box filter of $2\mu\text{Hz}$. Low frequencies cut out due to the high pass filter are not shown, and slight ripples visible $< 1000 \mu\text{Hz}$ in the PSD are artifacts of the high-pass filter used to flatten the light curve, and not physical.

secutive residual points $> 3\sigma$ away from the median (where σ is the median absolute deviation of the normalized light curve).

Step 5: Compute both a power spectrum and power spectral density for all light curve groups using a Lomb-Scargle, (Lomb (1976); Scargle (1982)) from the Astropy library (Astropy Collaboration et al. 2018) package, up to the Nyquist frequency of $25000 \mu\text{Hz}$. The power spectrum is critically sampled with a frequency resolution of $\Delta\nu_T$ equal to the inverse of the time series duration. Smooth the resulting PSD using a box-filter of $2 \mu\text{Hz}$ for visual inspection.

The primary steps of this pipeline are shown in Figure 4.

6. METHODS

We search for oscillations in the power spectra in two separate ways. One is a simple visual inspection, to see if any strong signals are clearly present and above 4 times the mean noise level. For signals that may be too weak to clearly manifest themselves though, we also develop an algorithm to search for them. We base it on the idea

that signals with low S/N will still have many consecutive frequency bins with slightly higher power, which could still be detectable even if no singular frequency peaks significantly.

6.1. Testing for Power Excess

The algorithm we use is based on the fact that the power of the oscillation modes in a star appear in a Gaussian envelope centered on the maximum oscillation frequency, ν_{max} . If oscillations are present, then there will be a power excess within this Gaussian envelope (see Figure 5). We assume that the frequency bins in the PSD are independent, and that the noise in each bin is distributed according to a χ^2 distribution with two degrees of freedom (Basu & Chaplin 2017). These assumptions are not entirely correct, as PDCSAP light curves have gaps in the data which cause correlation between the frequency bins of the resulting periodogram (Pascual-Granado et al. 2018). Gaps can arise when data points are filtered out due to bad quality (due to events such as pixel saturation, or cosmic ray hits; Twicken et al. 2020) or can be periodic in nature due to data downloads during each orbit. However, we make the assumption that these gaps – of around 1 day at their largest if stitching together consecutive light curves

Figure 5. Upper Panel: In blue the PSD of a light curve of the M dwarf HIP 56998 from our sample, with an injected solar oscillation at $2330 \mu\text{Hz}$. In orange is the background estimate, and the power in the envelope is distributed within the black Gaussian envelope. Bottom Panel: The likelihood of the null hypothesis returned from our detection algorithm for this PSD.

– are small enough so as not to have major effects on our results. This follows what other authors have done who use similar detection methods, and whose work we base our algorithm on (Nielsen et al. 2022).

The Gaussian envelope that centers on the solar oscillations can be characterized by their central frequency and full width half maximum (FWHM). Both of these parameters scale with ν_{max} and T_{eff} (see Chaplin et al. 2011). For stars with $T_{\text{eff}} \leq 5600\text{K}$, such as the stars we are examining, these parameters depend only on ν_{max} . We can therefore calculate the expected oscillation envelope centered on any frequency bin in our spectrum, and test the power excess inside of it. We take as our H_0 hypothesis that the power in the envelope is consistent with the spectrum’s background noise level, and look for frequencies where the probability of H_0 is low. While other types of variability (such as transits or rotations) would typically produce false positives with this method, the majority of these signals should have been filtered out with the high-pass filtering described above.

For stars with temperatures below 5600 K the solar-oscillations envelope is predicted as a Gaussian power distribution with a FWHM that scales with the center frequency:

$$\Gamma_{\text{E}} = .66 \left(\frac{\nu_{\text{max}}}{\mu\text{Hz}} \right)^{.88}$$

These relations are derived by (Mosser et al. 2012) from fits to the power spectra of *Kepler* targets. These have not been calibrated for M dwarfs, but we use them as a basis for our algorithm regardless and sum the power within the range $\nu_{\text{max}} \pm \Gamma_{\text{E}}/2$.

We evaluate the likelihood of H_0 as being given by a χ^2 distribution with $2N_b$ degrees of freedom, where N_b is the number of frequency bins in the envelope. For a given Gaussian envelope centered on a certain frequency bin we can compute the H_0 likelihood as

$$\mathcal{L}(T_i|H_0) = \chi_{2N_b}^2(T_i) = \frac{T_i^{N_b-1}}{2^{N_b}\Gamma(N_b)} e^{-T_i}$$

where our test statistic $T_i = \sum_{i-N_b/2}^{i+N_b/2} s_i$, where s_i is the signal strength for frequency bin i , given by the power p_i of the PSD divided by the background noise estimate b_i . To estimate the background noise we use a non-parametric log-median filter, which computes the median power for a set of evenly spaced frequency bins in log frequency space. This method allows us to capture any granulation power or spectral leakage at low frequencies, before becoming essentially constant at higher frequencies. See Figure 5 for an example of the algorithm applied on a sample power spectra.

6.2. Signal Injection Testing

We perform signal injection and recovery tests to verify that our algorithm reliably recovers oscillations from the data. We generate synthetic solar oscillations using the AsteroFLAG Artificial Dataset Generator 3 (AADG3), which simulates light curves of solar like oscillators (Ball et al. 2018). Oscillations are generated using the Laplace transform solution of a damped harmonic oscillator (Chaplin et al. 1997), with an addition of a correlated excitation component to produce mode asymmetry (Toutain et al. 2006). We set the parameters to produce a 27.4 d observation of a solar oscillator taken by *TESS* in the 20 s cadence mode, giving the stochastic driving term 6 d to build up from zero. We center the oscillations at $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2450 \mu\text{Hz}$ with a $\Delta\nu = 75 \mu\text{Hz}$, typical values for a solar oscillation in a low-luminosity red giant. While these frequencies are lower than those expected for both the ν_{max} and $\Delta\nu$ parameters of oscillations in an M dwarf, they are sufficient for the purposes of signal injection and recovery. A sample injected signal can be seen in Figure 6.

The amplitudes of each of the modes that make up the solar oscillations can be estimated from the scaling relation described in Equation 3. In reality, the actual apparent amplitudes are usually lower due to geometric effects, namely cancellation and inclination. Cancelling occurs as the angular degree ℓ increases and an increas-

Figure 6. Solar-like oscillation signal injected into SC PSC-SAP TESS light curve for TIC 192468220. Upper panel: PSD plot between $[200, 20000]$ μHz smoothed over $1 \mu\text{Hz}$. Bottom Panel: Normalized PSD, between $[1500, 2500]$ μHz .

ing amount of equally sized brighter and darker regions appear across a star’s surface (Kurtz 2022). These cancel out when integrating over the surface, which can be quantified as the normalized visibility parameter \tilde{V}_ℓ which describes the visibility of any non-radial mode as compared to the radial one. AADG3 estimates these visibilities using the median normalized visibilities for the main-sequence stars studied by Lund et al. (2017), but these visibilities are influenced by the photometric bandpass and will likely be different from ones in actual *TESS* data. The other principal effect affecting the visibility of the mode amplitudes is the inclination angle of the rotating star which influences the visibility of modes with different azimuthal orders m . The visible power in each mode is the intrinsic power multiplied by a factor corresponding to their associated Legendre function (see Gizon & Solanki (2003) for details).

For the purposes of our signal injection here, we ignore the effects of these two mechanisms, and take the maximum visible power of the mode as its true power. We test a range of amplitudes injected across different

light curves from our sample, and find that our algorithm reliably picks up solar oscillations before they are have frequency spikes greater than 4σ and are clearly visible by eye. We define a detection by our algorithm as a prediction probability of H_0 less than .77, which Nielsen et al. (2022) determined to be the highest accuracy threshold for such a method based on a sample of 800 main sequence stars.

We also use our signal injection and recovery methods to help establish detection thresholds for the stars in our sample. For all of the light curves in our sample, we first generate the light curve of a solar oscillation as defined above. We then replicate the data gaps from our stellar light curve in our oscillation light curve, and add that resulting light curve onto the normalized stellar light curve. We then pass this resulting modified light curve into our regular pipeline, performing the processing described in Section 5 on it. We scale the A_{rms} amplitude of the injected oscillation to a range of values, and for each one test whether the oscillation can be reliably detected. This involved both testing whether the oscillation could be identified visually (passing the $S/N > 4$ threshold), and whether the power excess algorithm could detect it. We inject these oscillations into all of the M dwarfs in our sample, initially just into individual 27.4 d sectors so as to keep consistency across stars. We then dynamically produce light curve oscillations with durations equal to the stitched light curve groups of each star, and performed the same steps as above. The number of stars for which oscillations were detected as a function of the injected oscillation amplitude can be found in Figures 7 and 10. Notably, the detection threshold from our algorithm for each star is lower than simply 4 times the mean noise level. This is due to the power excess algorithm reliably picking up the oscillation before it grew to 4 times the noise. Going forward, we label our detection thresholds defined by the noise level as D_1 thresholds (for ease of comparison to previous studies that use this standard, like Rodríguez et al. 2016), and those defined by our algorithm as D_2 thresholds.

7. LIGHT CURVES

7.1. Sample S_1

A total of 436 individual light curve groups were produced by our pipeline, which were visually inspected to get a sense of the inherent stellar variation present in our sample. The majority of our targets showed some sign of stellar variability, which is to be expected for low-mass stars. 86% of them showed some sort of rotational modulation indicative of stable sun spots on the surface of the star, within which 40% showed strong rotational

Variability	Sample S_1	Sample S_2
Rotation	.88	.95
Flares	.89	.91
Transits	.021	.013
Eclipses	.014	.010

Table 2. Fraction of stars exhibiting different types of variability in their light curves, in both our S_1 and S_2 samples. The fraction of stars with measurable flares and rotation periods is similar across the two samples, likely due to their detection requirements being rather liberal.

modulation with a clear periodicity. Visible rotational modulation (but without necessarily a well-defined period) was defined as producing a spike with $\text{SNR} > 3$ in the flattened periodogram of the normalized light curve, where a $1 \mu\text{Hz}$ box-kernel was used to estimate the background noise level. Strong rotational modulation with a clear period needed to meet the same criteria but for a $\text{SNR} > 5$. These periods were searched for prior to detrending long periods from the data. A total of 83% of our stars showed at least one flare signature, with flares defined as having 3 or more consecutive residuals $> 3\sigma$ away from baseline in a flattened light curve. This follows the criteria outlined by [Chang et al. \(2015\)](#) and used by other authors in flare studies ([Davenport et al. 2020](#), [Ilin et al. 2019](#)). A small subset of the stars in our sample also showed eclipse or transit events. A summary of these different types of variability is listed in Table 2. $43 \pm 2\%$ of the stars in our sample were in binary or higher order systems. For these systems, the light from each star was often mixed in a single light curve, due to the large size of *TESS*'s pixels.

7.2. Sample S_2

We perform the same analysis described above on our extended sample S_2 . Out of our initial selection of 705 stars, 387 of them had at least one SC *TESS* observation. Again, many of the stars in our sample showed intrinsic variability due to rotation and flares. A full summary of the types of variability present can be found in Table 2. Overall the average flux of stars in our S_2 sample were larger than those in our S_1 sample (on order of 200000 vs 50000 e^-s^{-1}), due to the larger masses of stars in S_2 . Sample S_2 had similar rotation and flare rate occurrences, as well as percentage of transits and eclipses. This is somewhat unexpected, as more massive stars spin down and become inactive more quickly than low mass ones ([Popinchalk et al. 2021](#)). Thus stars with lower stellar masses are more likely to show rotation and flare signatures. This discrepancy between

Figure 7. Detection thresholds for stars in our S_1 sample. In red are the thresholds defined as four times the mean noise level, in blue are the thresholds determined using the Power Excess algorithm. Note that the thresholds found algorithmically are generally lower than those defined as simply four times the noise. Detection thresholds of the PE method are established by injecting solar oscillations of increasing amplitude until they are detected, corresponding to the amplitudes in ppm on the x-axis.

our results and theory can be explained by the fact that our requirements for an observation showing a flare are rather lenient, requiring only one flare signature of unspecified intensity. Additionally, the more massive stars are brighter and flares can be more easily detected in them. If we look instead at the number of flares each star has, we find that there are nearly twice as many low mass ones with multiple (> 10) distinct flares. Of the stars in our sample, 25% of them were in multiple star systems, with 17% of them being the primary star.

8. PERIODOGRAMS

8.1. Sample S_1

An associated periodogram was produced for each of the light curve groups from our pipeline, which were initially inspected by eye for solar-like oscillations. Figure 7 shows the detection thresholds achieved for our sample S_1 . D_1 detection thresholds between 2-100 ppm are achieved for 50% of the stars in our sample and between 2-300 ppm for 89% of them. We reach D_2 detection thresholds of 2.3–16 ppm for 50% of these stars. It is important to note that these thresholds are not corrected for the fact that some of our light curves are dominated by the contaminant flux of a companion star. Of the 7 M dwarfs with the lowest nominal detection thresholds in our sample ($D_1 < 10$ ppm), none of them are the primary star in their system. All are in orbit with a brighter main sequence star. As $22 \pm 2\%$ of our stars reside in systems where they are not the primary, we

Figure 8. Oscillations detected in the light curve for GJ 231 B, which is the secondary companion to the G7 star α Mensae. Left Panel: Power spectrum density in range $[200,25000]$ μHz , smoothed by $2\mu\text{Hz}$, with oscillations visible around $3250 \mu\text{Hz}$. Right Panel: PSD plot zoomed in on $[2500,4000]$ μHz .

must carefully vet any potential signals to be sure they are from the M dwarf itself.

We do not find any significant peaks that are indicative of solar-like oscillations in an M dwarf. The majority of our periodograms are flat over the entirety of the frequency space, and no detections are returned by our algorithm either. We identify 15 signals with a SNR > 4 , nine of which belong to stars in multiple-star systems. These signals with prominent peaks can either be attributed to transits or eclipses in the light curve, stellar rotations with frequencies above our high pass filter, or oscillations of a companion solar, sub-giant, or giant star, whose flux contaminated the observation. The six signals coming from singular star systems are all high-frequency aliases of lower frequency signals, primarily transits and ultra-fast rotations. These stars are listed in Table 3, along with the SNR of their strongest signal, its frequency, and the likely physical mechanism causing it. Sample signals can be found in Figures 8 and 9, which show a system containing eclipses and another containing solar-like oscillations from a companion star, respectively.

8.2. Sample S_2

As in Sample S_1 , a periodogram was calculated for each set of stitched light curves. Since sample S_2 consisted of larger mass and brighter stars, our detection thresholds were on average better than those in sample S_1 . We reached D_1 detection thresholds of $2 - 10$ ppm for 17% of the stars in our sample, and $2 - 50$ ppm for 92% of them. Our D_2 detection thresholds were even

Figure 9. Top Panel: *TESS* light curve of GJ 630.1 (CM Draconis), an eclipsing binary system of two red dwarfs. Bottom Panel: Power spectrum of the light curve, with spikes in the power due to transits visible. The red line is at 4 times the mean noise level.

lower, between $0.5-5$ ppm for 20% of our stars. Both

Star	SNR	ν_{\max} μHz	Mechanism
GJ 231 B	4	3227	Companion S-O
GJ 67 B	4	2200	Companion S-O
GJ 61 B	4	1500	Companion S-O
LHS 1809	7	130	Ultra Fast Rot
SCR J0838-5855 A	7	118	Ultra Fast Rot
LSPM 1422-7023	7	116	Ultra Fast Rot
SCR J0754-3809	5	109	Ultra Fast Rot
SCR 2049-4012 B	8	105	Ultra Fast Rot
LHS 6167 A	21	100	Ultra Fast Rot
LHS 6167 B	22	90	Ultra Fast Rot
LMC 194.6.41	6	70	Ultra Fast Rot
GJ 473 A	7	55	Eclipse
LHS 3844	6	23	Transit
GJ 630.1 B	40	9	Eclipse
GJ 1253	14	.8	Transit

Table 3. Stars showing signals with $\text{SNR} > 4$, as well as the frequency of the signal and the likely cause of it.

sets of detection thresholds are summarized in Figure 10.

Due to the larger size of the sample, we performed an initial selection of periodograms of the flattened light curves that had peaks greater than 4σ , which were flagged as candidates and given highest importance. 6% of our periodograms met this criteria. These were inspected most closely and in some cases followed up on. After this initial investigation was completed, all of the periodograms were inspected visually and run through our PE algorithm. Again, we could not reliably attribute any of the signals in the periodograms to oscillations of an M dwarf, although several strong signals, some of them solar oscillations of nearby stars, were indeed found. Some notable systems recovered from our analysis that showed strong oscillations were the triple system 94 Aquarii (which hosts an M dwarf in an outer orbit) and the binary α Circ.

Strong signals resembling oscillations were also found in three systems which had not been previously reported. These were GJ 190, GJ 438, and GJ 531. We ran these IDs through Simbad to learn more about each star, and found no literature on any of them. Two of them, GJ 190 and GJ 438, are in both our sub-sample from the CNS5 dataset as well as the bright M dwarf catalog, while GJ 531 is only in the sub-sample we drew.

GJ 438 (TIC 93716498) is located at $(\text{RA}_{\alpha\text{J2016}}, \text{DEC}_{\delta\text{J2016}}) = (292.3578 +09.6274)$. It has an estimated mass of $0.43M_{\odot}$ and is around 11 pc away. It has one

Figure 10. Detection thresholds for stars in our S_2 sample. In red are the thresholds defined as four times the mean noise level, in blue are the thresholds determined using the Power Excess algorithm.

Figure 11. Upper Panel: GJ 438 light curve zoomed in on a 1 day interval. Rapid rotational modulation is visible. Lower Panel: Zoomed in PSD of the above light curve, centered at $315 \pm 175 \mu\text{Hz}$, smoothed using a box filter of $2 \mu\text{Hz}$.

SC observation taken in Sector 37, and at first inspection shows variability but with no clear rotational period. It exhibits frequency spikes in its PSD resembling solar-like oscillations, with a PSD peak at $318 \mu\text{Hz}$, that reaches a $\text{SNR} > 30$ (Figure 11). There are no reported companions in any catalogs or in Simbad. The frequency of ν_{\max} is again lower than expected for one originating from an M dwarf. Closer examination of a binned light curve reveals that this is in fact an extremely fast rotating star,

Figure 12. Left Panels: light curve and corresponding PSD of GJ 190, with the PSD zoomed in on $680 \pm 190 \mu\text{Hz}$, smoothed using a box filter of $2 \mu\text{Hz}$. Right Panel: light curve and corresponding PSD of GJ 531, with the PSD zoomed in on $900 \pm 600 \mu\text{Hz}$, smoothed using a box filter of $2 \mu\text{Hz}$.

with a period of just under an hour that was able to survive our high pass filter. Several studies have been done on ultrafast rotating M dwarfs, and even within this context GJ 438 is very fast. In previous studies of ultrafast rotating low mass stars observed with TESS, the shortest period found was 1.3 hours (Ramsay et al. 2020). With a rotational period of 55 min, GJ 438 is even lower than this.

GJ 190 (TIC 146538232) is located at $(\text{RA}_{\alpha\text{J2016}}, \text{DEC}_{\delta\text{J2016}}) = (218.9066, -30.6032)$. Its mass is estimated at around $0.61M_{\odot}$, and it is located approximately 9.2 pc away. It has one SC observation taken in Sector 32, and shows variability but without a clear rotational period. A closer look at its PSD reveals solar-like oscillations around $\nu_{\text{max}} \approx 680 \mu\text{Hz}$ (Figure 12). These frequencies are lower than expected than for ones caused by solar-like oscillations in an M dwarf. While no companions are listed in CNS5, Simbad lists this star as a double or multiple system. It seems likely that these oscillations originate from a companion/nearby star, not the M dwarf itself.

GJ 531 (TIC 241682179) is located at $(\text{RA}_{\alpha\text{J2016}}, \text{DEC}_{\delta\text{J2016}}) = (312.6747 +10.7894)$. It was only in our sample as part of our filtering of the CNS5 database, and was not originally included in the bright M dwarfs catalog. It’s absolute K-band magnitude is 5.2, putting it at one of the brightest stars in our sample, and with a mass estimate of $0.62M_{\odot}$. A closer analysis of its light curve shows a strong frequency spike at $94.1 \mu\text{Hz}$ with spikes at higher frequency integer multiples as well,

and that the signal is in fact not a solar-like oscillation. At periods of a few hours, these frequency spikes could be produced by rapid rotation of the star, the signal of which leaked through the high-pass filter. Examining the smoothed light in Figure 12 curve shows clear, periodic amplitude modulations that support this interpretation. A more thorough literature search revealed that this star is also in a catalog of late-type members of young stellar kinematic groups (Montes et al. 2001). This agrees with the rapid rotational modulations we see evidence of, as these young stars can rotate at very high speeds.

We achieve D_2 detection thresholds of below 1ppm for 9 of the stars in our study. Seven of these are in multi-star systems though, where there is a possibility of a nearby star’s light contamination. Two of them are singular star systems, and are shown in Figure 13. These two, GJ 651 and HIP 30862, have detection thresholds of approximately 0.9 ppm. They have masses of about $0.63M_{\odot}$ and $0.57M_{\odot}$, and are located at 18.3 pc and 24.5 pc away, respectively. Neither of them show clear indication of solar-like oscillations, and nor do the other seven.

9. SUMMED POWER SPECTRA

We co-add the power spectra of similar mass stars across all of our samples to see if weak strength signals are revealed. In theory, stars with similar masses will have solar-like oscillations at similar frequencies and with similar frequency spacing (from Equation 1), and

Figure 13. Power spectral density plots and corresponding power excess probabilities of the two M dwarfs in our sample with the lowest thresholds and no nearby stars (GJ 651 on the left, HIP 30862 on the right). The orange curve shows the background estimate of the PSD, and the red line shows the $P(H_0) = .77$ line.

thus when their power spectra are summed the noise could cancel out while their signals co-add constructively. We group stars in our original and extended sample from 0.1 to $0.6 M_{\odot}$ in bins of $0.02 - 0.05 M_{\odot}$, and co-add their power spectra. We remove from the sum any power spectra which were previously identified as having strong signals, such as those belonging to stars with transits, very high rotation frequencies, or non M dwarf companion oscillators. We weigh each spectra by its detection threshold, to account for both the brightness of the star and the number of observations for it. Our co-added power spectra, normalized using a running median, are displayed in Figure 14. No clear signals are revealed from summing the power spectra, and none are found by running our PE algorithm on these summed power spectra either.

We test how effective co-adding the power spectra is by injecting synthetic signals into our data at low amplitudes, and seeing if the resulting power spectra of similarly massed stars co-add constructively. We sample groups of 20 synthetic solar oscillation light curves from the dataset compiled by Ball et al. 2018 that all have masses within 10% of each other. Ball et al.’s dataset also lists radii and effective temperatures for each star, generated from stellar evolution models. We inject these oscillations into M dwarf light curves from our sample, and co-add the resulting modified light curves. We find that the oscillations do not co-add constructively, and that weak signals do not become more prominent after summing the power spectra. This is likely due to the

small variations in mass, radius, and temperature creating different enough $\Delta\nu$ and ν_{\max} values to keep the narrow frequency spikes of the oscillation signals from adding constructively. As an example, a random sample of 20 stars from the catalog with masses between $1.10 - 1.15$ and corresponding radii within 10% of each other have a range of ν_{\max} values of $70 \mu\text{Hz}$. These offsets, along with small variations in $\Delta\nu$, could keep signals from co-adding constructively. The masses sampled for our synthetic oscillations are higher (around $1 M_{\odot}$) than those in our actual sample, but the results translate to lower mass stars as well, which have even larger expected $\Delta\nu$ values and a wider range of possible ν_{\max} values.

10. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We have presented the results of a search for solar-like oscillations in M dwarfs in the *TESS* 20 second cadence data base. We began with an initial sample of the 512 M dwarfs with masses between $0.1 - 0.3 M_{\odot}$ within 15 pc, from the catalog compiled by Winters et al. (2021). We extended our sample using the Fifth Catalogue of Nearby Stars and selecting only M dwarfs within 25pc that satisfied our *JHK* photometry conditions, as well as incorporating the Nearby Bright M Dwarfs catalogue. This resulted in an additional 705 stars. Out of this combined sample of 1217 stars, 868 of them had at least one SC *TESS* observation. All of these observations passed through our pipeline, aimed at producing cleaned, normalized, flattened light curves with the longest baseline

Figure 14. Normalized, co-added spectra of stars in our sample in mass bins of $0.05M_{\odot}$, starting at $0.1 - 0.15M_{\odot}$, and increasing to the right ($0.15 - 0.2M_{\odot}$) and downwards, with the bottom right plot being the $0.55 - 0.6M_{\odot}$ bin.

possible to calculate a periodogram from. Many of the stars in our sample exhibited intrinsic variability in their light curves, including flares, sun-spot rotational modulation, transits, eclipses, and solar-oscillations due to nearby, higher mass companion stars.

Our D_1 detection thresholds are between 10-100 ppm for 50% of stars in our S_1 sample, and between 2-20 ppm for 50% of stars in our S_2 sample, which are larger and brighter. These detection thresholds are slightly higher than the detection thresholds of previous M dwarf oscillation searches, done with *Kepler* (Rodríguez et al. 2016). This is due to *Kepler*'s longer baseline and higher photometric precision compared to *TESS*. Our D_2 detection thresholds for our S_2 sample stars are significantly better though, and on par with the thresholds of previous *Kepler* oscillation searches. With several hundred stars in our S_2 sample, this makes our study the largest sample size and highest frequency search for solar-like

oscillations in M dwarfs to date, with comparable to or better sensitivity than previous ones.

Overall, we do not find any signs of solar-like oscillations originating from an M dwarf. This result is not entirely surprising, given that the majority of our detection thresholds are above the very low expected amplitudes of solar oscillations in M dwarfs. For nine of the M dwarfs in our study we reached D_2 detection thresholds below 1 ppm, the lowest detection thresholds on oscillations for M dwarfs yet. This is within the range of expected amplitudes for M dwarf oscillations, but still no clear oscillations are visible. This can be explained by the fact that the apparent visibility of the oscillation modes is likely lower than their true maximum amplitude, due to cancellation and inclination effects.

Future work will include running more sophisticated algorithms optimized for detecting low amplitude oscillations on the sample compiled here. More effective ways of co-adding the power spectra should also be

investigated, to avoid the limitations described above. It is challenging to reach higher detection sensitivities through *TESS* data alone, and the major advances in the search for solar-like oscillations in M dwarfs will likely be made by more sensitive instruments. *JWST* has higher sensitivity but likely does not have the short cadence needed to detect solar oscillations. Other space telescopes like *PLATO* are more promising and will soon be delivering interesting data with cadences of just 25s (Bétrisey et al. 2023). *PLATO*'s smaller pixel size (15" x 15") will also make it less likely for M dwarf light curves to be contaminated by nearby stars, and the high duration of each pointing (2+ years) will allow for a much longer baseline. High sensitivity radial velocity instruments that are coming online, like the IGRINS-2 spectrograph (Lee et al. 2022), could also play an important role in detecting these elusive oscillations.

M dwarfs remain a class of star on the main sequence for which no solar-like oscillations have been detected. The discovery of them would be of high value to our understanding of their inner structure, the planetary systems they often host, and how solar-like oscillations scale to smaller stars. Their detection remains an important scientific goal, and one which may be well suited for the next generation of photometric and spectroscopic instruments.

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